

A CORRELATIONAL ANALYSIS OF SEMANTIC SKILLS IN RELATION TO SEX AND YEAR LEVEL AMONG PHYSICAL EDUCATION MAJORS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20039594>

ABSTRACT

In this study, the researchers explored the relationship between semantic skills, sex, and academic year level among Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Physical Education (BPEd) students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated (SVCI). This research utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational design involving sixty-seven (67) BPEd students from first to fourth year. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire administered via Google Forms using a self-made Likert scale to assess semantic skills. The instrument showed excellent reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.91). Data were analyzed using a weighted mean to determine the level of semantic skills, a Chi-square test for the relationship between sex and semantic skills, and a Kruskal-Wallis H test for differences across year levels at a 0.05 level of significance. Results showed that female students across all year levels and male students in the third and fourth years obtained a "Good" level of semantic skills, while first- and second-year male students yielded "Acceptable." Overall, BPEd students demonstrated adequate semantic competence. Findings further revealed no significant relationship between sex and semantic skills and no significant difference across academic year levels, proving that semantic skills are generally consistent regardless of sex and academic year level. It is recommended to strengthen semantic skills development through targeted instructional programs.

Keywords: *semantic skills, Physical Education Majors, sex, academic year level, descriptive-correlational analysis, St. Vincent's College Incorporated*

INTRODUCTION

At present, enhancing students' language comprehension and communication skills has been a central concern of educational institutions worldwide. Semantics, as a branch of linguistics that deals with word meaning, plays a crucial role in improving learners' understanding of words, sentences, discourse, and context (Harara, 2021). Semantic knowledge helps learners interpret meaning across linguistic forms and understand how meaning is constructed in communication settings (Hussein & Mohammed, 2022). By fostering semantic awareness, learners are better equipped to interpret and produce coherent messages in diverse communicative contexts (Siregar & Damanik, 2025).

Semantic skills are essential for effective communication because they enable learners to express ideas clearly and interpret messages accurately (Zano, 2022). However, limited semantic competence can lead to misunderstanding and communication breakdowns (Nation, 2022). Meaning-related difficulties such as ambiguity and contextual misinterpretation can also disrupt communication in classroom interaction (Cutting & Fordyce, 2020).

Despite theoretical understanding of semantics, there remains a gap in applied research focusing on learners' characteristics. Many studies emphasize linguistic theory rather than classroom application of semantic competence (Khaksar & Khaghaninejad, 2024). Limited research also explores how semantic skills vary according to learner variables such as gender and academic level (Rustan & Rachmat, 2024).

Furthermore, semantic development is essential for academic success across disciplines. Students with strong semantic knowledge are better able to interpret instructions, think critically, and engage in discussions (Nation, 2022). Conversely, learners with weak semantic skills often struggle with comprehension and expression, which negatively affects academic performance and motivation (Harara, 2021).

Against this background, the researchers conducted this study to describe and analyze the relationship between semantic skills, sex, and academic year level among BPEd students at SVCI. By addressing this practical knowledge gap, the study sought to provide insights into the applied use of semantics in educational contexts and contribute to strategies for enhancing students' linguistic competencies.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the relationship between semantic skills, sex, and academic year level among Physical Education students at SVCI through a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the demographic profiles of the BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated in terms of:

- 1.1 sex; and
- 1.2 year level?
2. What is the level of semantic skills among BPEd Students of St. Vincent's College Incorporated?
3. Is there a significant relationship between sex and the semantic skills of the BPEd students of St. Vincent's College Incorporated?
4. Is there a significant difference in semantic skills among BPEd students of St. Vincent's College Incorporated across academic year levels?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design using a survey questionnaire as the primary tool for data collection. Descriptive analysis was used to determine the level of semantic skills of the respondents when grouped according to sex and academic year level. Correlational and comparative analyses were applied to examine the relationship between sex and semantic skills, as well as the differences in semantic skills across year levels.

The respondents consisted of sixty-seven (67) BPEd students from first to fourth year, both male and female, enrolled at St. Vincent's College Incorporated. A non-probability sampling technique, specifically convenience sampling, was used in selecting the participants. This method was chosen based on the accessibility and availability of the respondents, allowing the researchers to gather data efficiently within a limited time frame.

To collect the required data, a structured questionnaire was administered through Google Forms. The instrument included items designed to measure the semantic skills of the respondents using a self-made Likert scale with the following ratings: 5 (Very Good), 4 (Good), 3 (Acceptable), 2 (Poor), and 1 (Very Poor). The instrument was pilot tested to ensure validity and reliability, yielding a Cronbach's alpha of 0.91, which indicates excellent internal consistency.

The data gathering process followed systematic procedures. The researchers first prepared a research plan and secured permission from the appropriate authorities and participants. The questionnaire was then developed and distributed online via Google Forms. Respondents were given two (2) weeks to complete the survey at their own pace. After all responses were collected, the data were retrieved from the platform, then organized, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly.

The following statistical tools were used to address the research questions of the study. The Weighted Mean was used to determine the level of semantic skills of the respondents when grouped according to sex and year level, based on the Likert scale interpretations. The Chi-Square Test was employed to determine whether a significant relationship exists between sex and the semantic skills of the respondents. The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was used to determine whether a significant difference in semantic skills

exists when respondents are grouped according to year level. All hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Figure 1
Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Sex

Figure 1 illustrates the demographic profile of the BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated in terms of sex. Of the sixty-seven (67) total respondents, thirty-seven (37) were female, accounting for 55.2% of the population, while thirty (30) were male, representing 44.8%. This indicates that the majority of the respondents were female.

Figure 2
Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Year Level

Figure 2 illustrates the demographic profile of the BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated in terms of year level. Of the sixty-seven (67) total respondents, the first-year students comprised the largest group with twenty-four (24) respondents, representing 35.8% of the total population. This was followed by third-year students with twenty-two (22) respondents, accounting for 32.8%. Second-year students ranked third with sixteen (16) respondents, comprising 23.9%, while fourth-year students had the fewest respondents with only five (5), representing 7.5%. Overall, the data reveal that the majority of the respondents were from the lower year levels, particularly first and third year, suggesting a higher enrollment concentration in these levels within the BPEd program at St. Vincent's College Incorporated.

Table 1
Weighted Mean of the Semantic Skills of BPEd Students by Sex and Year Level

Sex	Year Level	Mean	Interpretation
F	1st	3.64	Good
M	1st	3.29	Acceptable
F	2nd	3.70	Good
M	2nd	3.37	Acceptable
F	3rd	3.56	Good
M	3rd	3.81	Good
F	4th	3.57	Good
M	4th	3.60	Good

Table 1 presents the weighted mean scores of the semantic skills of BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated grouped by sex and year level. Results show that female students across all year levels obtained a "Good" verbal interpretation, with means ranging from 3.56 to 3.70. Male students in the third and fourth year likewise obtained a "Good" interpretation, with means of 3.81 and 3.60, respectively. However, male students in the first and second year obtained an "Acceptable" interpretation, with means of 3.29 and 3.37, respectively. Overall, the majority of the respondents demonstrated a good level of semantic skills.

Table 2
Chi-Square Test on the Relationship Between Sex and Semantic Skills of BPEd Students

Chi-square value	Level of Significance	Interpretation
0.99	0.05	No significant relationship

Table 2 presents the results of the Chi-Square Test examining the relationship between sex and the semantic skills of BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated. The obtained chi-square value of 0.99 at a 0.05 level of significance indicates no significant relationship between sex and semantic skills. This means that the semantic skills of the respondents do not significantly vary based on sex.

Table 3
Kruskal-Wallis Test on the Difference in Semantic Skills of BPEd Students Across Year Levels

P-value	Level of Significance	Interpretation
0.99	0.05	No significant difference

Table 3 presents the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H Test examining the difference in semantic skills among BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated across academic year levels. The obtained p-value of 0.99 at a 0.05 level of significance indicates no significant difference in semantic skills across year levels. This suggests that academic year level does not significantly influence the semantic skills of the respondents.

DISCUSSION

Figure 1 presents the demographic profile of the BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated in terms of sex. Among the first-year participants, there were sixteen (16) females and eight (8) males. The second-year respondents included six (6) females and ten (10) males, while the third-year group consisted of twelve (12) females and ten (10) males. For the fourth-year level, there were three (3) females and two (2) males. The data indicate that females generally outnumber males across most year levels, except in the second year where males were more represented. This distribution suggests a relatively balanced representation of both sexes, which allows for a more reliable comparison of semantic skills across sex.

Figure 2 illustrates the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of academic year level. The total number of participants was sixty-seven (67), with twenty-four (24) from the first year, sixteen (16) from the second year, twenty-two (22) from the third year, and five (5) from the fourth year. The results show that the majority of respondents came from the first and third year levels, while the fourth year had the fewest participants. This uneven distribution may reflect enrollment trends and could influence the overall interpretation of semantic skill levels across year levels. However, the presence of respondents from all year levels still provides a basis for comparison in the study.

Table 1 presents the weighted mean scores of the semantic skills of BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated grouped by sex and year level. Based on the results, female students across all year levels obtained a "Good" verbal interpretation.

Similarly, male students in the third and fourth year levels also achieved a "Good" rating. In contrast, male students in the first and second year levels obtained an "Acceptable" level of semantic skills. These findings indicate that the semantic skills of BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated are not deficient but fall within acceptable to good levels, suggesting that students generally possess adequate ability to understand and interpret the meanings of words, phrases, and contexts, which are essential for effective communication and academic performance.

Table 2 presents the results of the Chi-Square Test examining the relationship between sex and the semantic skills of BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated. With a total of sixty-seven (67) respondents and a 0.05 level of significance, the computed chi-square value of 0.99 exceeds the alpha value of 0.05, indicating no significant relationship between sex and semantic skills. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This finding suggests that semantic abilities are comparable between male and female students and are not influenced by sex. This result is supported by recent research of Maleki & Davaribina (2025), which found no meaningful gender-based differences in vocabulary-related reading comprehension performance among EFL learners.

Table 3 presents the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H Test examining the difference in semantic skills among BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated across academic year levels. With a 0.05 level of significance, the computed p-value of 0.99 exceeds the alpha value of 0.05, indicating no significant difference in semantic skills across year levels. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that students' semantic abilities remain relatively consistent regardless of academic year level. The finding suggests that semantic skill development may not be solely dependent on progression in year level but may instead be influenced by other factors such as exposure, practice, and individual learning experiences. This result is consistent with the study of Ubamos (2020), which revealed that grade level did not significantly affect students' morphemic and semantic analysis skills.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are hereby drawn.

The demographic profile of the BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated in terms of sex revealed that among the first-year participants, there were sixteen (16) females and eight (8) males. The second-year respondents included six (6) females and ten (10) males, while the third-year group consisted of twelve (12) females and ten (10) males. The fourth-year respondents comprised three (3) females and two (2) males, bringing the total number of participants to sixty-seven (67). In terms of academic year level, there were twenty-four (24) first-year participants, sixteen (16) from the second year, twenty-two (22) from the third year, and five (5) from the fourth year.

The weighted mean scores indicate that female students across all year levels obtained a "Good" verbal interpretation. Male students in the third and fourth year levels likewise obtained a "Good" rating, while male students in the first and second year levels obtained an "Acceptable" verbal interpretation. These results suggest that the semantic

skills of BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated are not deficient, falling within acceptable to good levels overall.

The Chi-Square Test revealed no significant relationship between sex and the semantic skills of the BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated, as the computed chi-square value of 0.99 exceeds the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, concluding that semantic skills do not significantly vary based on sex.

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test revealed no significant difference in semantic skills across academic year levels, as the computed p-value of 0.99 exceeds the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, concluding that academic year level does not significantly influence the semantic skills of the BPEd students at St. Vincent's College Incorporated.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Sex and year level should not be considered as determining factors of semantic skills, as the results indicate no significant relationship between these variables and the semantic skills of the respondents.
2. Schools are encouraged to implement a Semantic Skills Program within their curriculum to ensure that students develop the ability to understand and use words accurately and appropriately. If a separate program is not feasible, the integration and enhancement of semantics within regular classroom instruction should be prioritized.
3. Since the goal of education is to develop knowledge and proficiency, semantic skills development should be embedded across all year levels to continuously monitor and evaluate students' progress and address areas of improvement.
4. Future researchers are encouraged to investigate the underlying factors that influence students' semantic skills, considering both students' and teachers' perspectives for a more comprehensive understanding of the subject.
5. Researchers conducting similar studies are encouraged to include participants from different academic programs or institutions to broaden the scope and applicability of the findings.
6. It is recommended to provide students with learning materials focused on semantics prior to assessment and to explore effective instructional activities that can further enhance students' semantic abilities.
7. Teachers are encouraged to continuously assess the skills and competencies of their students to identify areas of deficiency and to provide appropriate interventions that will help develop their abilities, preparing them to become globally competitive individuals. Particular emphasis should be given to semantics, as it is a fundamental component of the teaching and learning process.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors affirm that this study was conducted in strict adherence to ethical research standards. Informed consent was secured from all respondents prior to data collection, ensuring that they were fully aware of the nature, purpose, and scope of the study. All respondents retained the right to withdraw at any point during the research process without consequence or prejudice. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were carefully upheld, and all data gathered were handled in compliance with established privacy protocols to safeguard their personal information.

Beyond the protection of respondents, the researchers likewise upheld the highest standards of academic integrity throughout the conduct of the study. The research was carried out with full transparency and free from any conflict of interest, ensuring that no external influence affected the credibility of its outcomes. All ideas, works, and references drawn from other sources were properly cited and acknowledged, and plagiarism in all its forms was strictly avoided. The findings derived from the study were analyzed and presented with complete objectivity and impartiality, and were utilized exclusively for legitimate research and academic purposes.

Acknowledgments

The authors sincerely thank God for guidance and strength throughout this study. Gratitude is also extended to the researchers' families, friends, and support systems for their unfaltering encouragement and assistance. The authors expressed appreciation to their research adviser and the panel of experts for their valuable feedback and contributions to this manuscript.

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